

NFDI4Chem, Chemistry Consortium in the NFDI

Activity Update

Open documentation of NFDI cross-cutting activities related to NFDI4Chem on the portal

TA1 - Management

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Contributing partner(s): all partners

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Executive summary

The NFDI e.V. currently contains 26 consortia, NFDI4Chem being one of them. Regular communication within the NFDI, i.e. with the headquarter as well as with other consortia, is part of the NFDI association structure and is crucial for the success of the overall project. Sections, Task forces and Circles allow cross-consortial cooperation and communication. The DFG is the funding agency for all NFDI consortia and needs to be involved in any matters related to the financial resources. An interim report (due on 30.09.2023) has to be submitted to the DFG.

Project objectives

This activity has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) Key Objective 5: Explore synergies with other consortia and promote cross-cutting development within the NFDI.

Detailed report on the activity

NFDI4Chem as a consortium of the NFDI e.V. ('consortium according to statutes') takes part in various cross-consortial activities within the association. The [sections](#) and related working groups work on cross-cutting topics (see [D6.3.1 cross-cutting topics](#)) together with experts from other consortia. The Task Force Evaluation & Reporting supports the consortia and directorate in the documentation of progress. [Regular meetings](#) of persons with similar roles or tasks enable the exchange of experiences, information and mutual support among the consortia.

Members of NFDI4Chem are engaging as spokespersons, co-organisers and/or participants in the following sections, working groups and NFDI community meetings (as of publication date):

- Consortium Assembly (Spokesperson 07/21 to 04/22: Christoph Steinbeck)
- Section Education & Training (Spokesperson: Sonja Herres-Pawlis)
 - Working group on target group and needs analysis (co-organiser: Sonja Herres-Pawlis)
 - Working Group Inventory Materials (Co-Organiser: Sonja Herres-Pawlis)
 - Working group Development of common, multidimensional teaching materials and establishment of a knowledge base, quality assurance and evaluation (see DALIA) (Co-organiser: Johannes Liermann)
 - Networking and Outreach Working Group (Co-Organiser: Sonja Herres-Pawlis)
 - Working Group on Dealing with Errors in Science (Organiser: John Joliffe)
- Section (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance (Speaker: Oliver Koepler)

- Working Group Ontology Harmonisation and Mapping (Organiser: Philip Strömert)
- Sektion Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects (Spokesperson: Franziska Böhm)
- Section Common Infrastructures
 - Working Group Data Management Planning (Co-Organiser: Daniela Hausen)
 - Working Group Electronic Lab Books (Co-Organisers: Nicole Jung, Felix Bach)
- Task Force Evaluation and Reporting (Participants: Franziska Eberl, Johannes Hunold)
- Speakers' Jour Fixe (Participants: Christoph Steinbeck, Oliver Koepler)
- Management Circle (Participant: Franziska Eberl)
- Communication Circle (Participant: Theo Bender)
- Finance Circle (Participant: Franziska Eberl)

The involvement of NFDI4Chem in cross-consortial activities within the NFDI e.V. is published on the [NFDI4Chem portal](#), which is regularly updated.

In addition to the above mentioned activities, members of NFDI4Chem, especially those being spokespersons of sections, have substantially contributed to the proposal for Base4NFDI ([Bernard et al. 2022](#)). Since 2023 [Base4NFDI](#) is funded by the DFG to support the development of basic services.

Communication to the DFG is maintained by TA1 and includes financial matters such as the yearly budget report or the submission of the interim report ([public part B1](#)). Whenever relevant, the communication to the DFG is coordinated among the consortia in the above-mentioned task force/ circles/ jour fixes.

Further updates of the cross-cutting activities within the NFDI will continuously be published on the NFDI4Chem portal.

References

Base4NFDI Website:

<https://base4nfdi.de/>

Bernard L, Altenhöner R, Böhm F, Diepenbroek M, Ebert B, Fluck J, et al. Base4NFDI - Basic Services for NFDI. Zenodo; 2022. [doi:10.5281/ZENODO.8329192](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8329192)

Hunold J, Koepler O, von Maltzan S, Klix M. Activity Update - Report of relevant cross-cutting topics for NFDI4Chem. Zenodo, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8334138>

NFDI Sections Overview:

<https://www.nfdi.de/sections/?lang=en>

NFDI Regular Community Meetings:

<https://www.nfdi.de/community-meetings/?lang=en>

Overview of cross-cutting activities on NFDI4Chem website:

<https://www.nfdi4chem.de/cross-consortium-activities-in-the-nfdi-e-v/>

Progress Report NFDI4Chem - B1:

<https://www.dfg.de/de/foerderung/foerderinitiativen/nfdi/zwischenberichte>

Abbreviations

NFDI - Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur